

**Nigeria Video Films and the Significant Roles of Costume and Make-Up:
A Study of Tchidi Chikere's "Worlds Apart".**

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Abstract

Film is a very powerful medium of communication if effectively packaged and deployed. It is a special medium of communication that transcends and surmounts the functional barriers of language and culture differences through the combination of the creative and communicative qualities of visual and audio effects. The Nigeria video film, is a proliferation of vital channel of information and education/edutainment to viewers. Significantly, it provides the function of cultural propagation and preservation of ethical values. It can also be a credible source of mass mobilization, being an influential force in changing human perception. On the other hand, the costume designer and make-up artist in a film production are the creative artists responsible for the fashion and appearances of the characters contributing generally to the production's inner meanings through their creative interpretations. Paradoxically, most Nigerian video films reveal a lack of credibility and professionalism especially in areas of costume and make-up. Oftentimes, the Nigeria video film is dominated by flamboyant costumes and make-ups, which do not match the realities on ground. Irrespective of the significance of the role of costume and make-up in drama, research reveals that it is an area that has not yet been given adequate attention in Nigeria video films. It was on this premise that the researcher embarked on this work with the view to ascertaining the functional role of costume and make-up in Nigeria video films.

Keywords: Video, Film, Communication, Costume and Make-up.

Le résumé

Le film est un moyen de communication très puissant s'il est efficacement emballé et utilisé. C'est un moyen de communication spécial qui transcende et surmonte les barrières fonctionnelles des différences linguistiques et culturelles par la combinaison des qualités créatives et communicatives des effets visuels et sonores. Le film vidéo du Nigeria, est une prolifération de canal vital de l'information et de l'éducation aux téléspectateurs. De manière significative, il fournit la fonction de propagation culturelle et de préservation des valeurs éthiques. Il peut également être une source crédible de mobilisation de masse, en tant que force influente dans la modification de la perception humaine. D'autre part, le créateur de costumes et maquilleur dans une production cinématographique sont les créateurs responsables de la mode et des apparences des personnages contribuant généralement aux significations intérieures de la production à travers leurs interprétations créatives. Paradoxalement, la plupart des films vidéo nigériens révèlent un manque de crédibilité et de professionnalisme notamment dans les domaines du costume et du maquillage. Souvent, le

film vidéo nigérian est dominé par des costumes et des maquillages flamboyants, qui ne correspondent pas aux réalités du terrain. Indépendamment de l'importance du rôle du costume et du maquillage dans le théâtre, la recherche révèle que c'est un domaine qui n'a pas encore reçu l'attention appropriée dans les films vidéo du Nigéria. C'est sur cette prémisse que le chercheur s'est lancé dans ce travail en vue de déterminer le rôle fonctionnel du costume et du maquillage dans les films vidéo du Nigéria.

Mots-clés : Vidéo, Film, Communication, Costume et maquillage

Introduction:

Film is a very powerful medium of mass communication when effectively packaged and employed. Dede Konkwo, noted that the film medium is unique because, "it transcends and surmounts the functional barriers of language and culture differences by the combination of the creative and communicative qualities of visual and audio effect" (72).

Considering the enormous quantity of movies churned out periodically, the Nigerian film industry called "Nollywood", is rated next to Hollywood and Bollywood, as the second largest film industry in the world. The Nigerian Video Film is a very vital medium of entertainment and education, significantly, serving as a cultural means of mass mobilization: as well as an influential force in changing human perceptions.

In the last three decades, the medium has explored considerable stories rooted in happenings within the Nigerian society. These are imaginatively retold through actors and actresses, using such visual elements of the theatre as costume, make-up, lighting, sets, locations and so on. A close survey of the Nigerian video film reveals that producers and directors usually focus on different themes such as: crime, violence, vengeance, politics, ritual, love, prostitution and infidelity, among others. Although the Nigeria video film explores themes drawn from social reality, such themes are packaged through artistic creations. Regrettably, a number of them reveal a lack of creativity in the handling of their stories. An assessment of the Nigeria video film production reveals that very often, sets, costume, make-up, location and shots are not well treated... With inadequate research on such vital visual elements of drama before designing, there is bound to be wrong pictures painted.

Costume in film is a language through which visual statements are made. Costumes are, therefore, categorized as "cultural documents" (Asiegbu, 2004). A good number of video films have good stories but fail in implementation, as revealed in the attempt to paint pictures not only larger than life but, extraordinary. The Nigeria video film is dominated by flamboyant costumes, and make-up, extravagantly furnished mansions, unnecessary display of wealth and the use of fashionable vehicles not in harmony with appropriate realities. In agreement with this, Adesanya states that "aesthetically... this is regrettably the métier of the home video movies: gaudy costumes, vulgarly furnished mansions and exotic vehicles" (13-20).

The costume designer in any film production is the creative artist responsible for the looks of the characters and thus contributes, generally to the production's inner meaning through his or her interpretations. He or she creates costumes for each of the characters in the play. Through this avenue the audience learns considerably about the wearer and his

environment. Little wonder that Opubor and Nwuneli submit that: "... it is believed that what many people know about other places is through film"(18). Thus, costume and make-up can be used to identify age, class, status or ethnic affiliation. The use of costume in any production, stage or screen could be negative and positive. Where appropriately applied, it is considered positive and negative when the reverse is the case. Research is thus very relevant to the film designer especially the costumer.

Irrespective of the significance of the role played by costume and make-up in drama, research reveals that it is an aspect not given adequate attention in Nigeria films. Where attention is drawn to it, there is a tendency towards exaggeration in its usage in character and scene portrayal. One should recommend that, this area of specialization calls for more critical study not only by drawing attention to the usefulness of costume and make-up in the creation of the ideal film image but to also point out the inadequacies traced to identifiable problems but also to advance appropriate use of costume and make-up.

Historical overview of the Nigeria video film

The Nigerian film emerged during the colonial period in the 19th century, under the British rule. According to Ekwuazi, "...what the colonialists did was that they integrated film into the development which is to say, to make the colonized people more amenable to colonialism ..."(2), thus, they showed the might of the British Empire. The films were also used to turn people's mind to colonial ideologies. Moreover, films made during this period were mostly documentary films. Examples of these films produced at this period include 'Mr. English at Home', 'Daybreak in Udi', among many others. These films listed did not really reflect the social and cultural life of the people. Thus, Onookome Okome states that:

The first set of film images that local populations saw was of white faces, doing outlandish things in their environment. These film images were far removed from the social reality of the indigenous people. As an art form, the film medium was not native to these people and since it was brought to them by the same social life. This attitude has persisted since colonial time (27).

This implies that, films produced during the colonial era did not reflect the social and cultural life of the people in the visual elements of film, especially costumes, Ekwuazi states that:

Film in the colonial period can be categorized in three stages: production, distribution, and exhibition. The production of these films during the colonial period was not done in the country. It only showed the involvement of the black people doing all the tedious jobs while the whites in the film stood as the initiators. These films were exhibited in schools, churches and hospitals. Moreover, distributions of the films were done by the colonial film unit (CFU) (9).

The first indigenous film production made its debut in 1970. The first film produced within this period was 'Kongi's Harvest'. It was produced by Francis Oladele. According to Francoise Balogun:

1970-80 was to prove fruitful decade with the first full length feature films

of some importance and the emergence of films in local languages (Ibo, Yoruba, and Hausa). Only a few films were produced (about twenty features film) but the technical quality improved greatly during these years and the Nigerian film industry made its mark not only locally but also internationally (47).

This also implies that the language of the film was English, but films in native language, Igbo, Yoruba, and Hausa emerged in the same decade. The technical quality improved greatly, especially in the area of costume and make-up, during these years. Also natural locations were used in place of symbolized studio environment. Furthermore, Balogun stated that, “the contribution of the Yoruba theatre practitioners in celluloid film making cannot be denied. The involvement of the Yoruba theatre practitioners in celluloid film making started in 1976 with the production of *Ajani Ogun* by Ola Balogun”(52). Ekwuazi opines that:

Most film makers come from what might be designated as the theatre belt of the country. That is; the south west of the country, with its virile theatre tradition and professional theatre companies. Some of these film makers have made name for themselves on stage before making the transition to film(20).

However, in 1980’s with the structural adjustment program (SAP) of Babangida, the production of films on celluloid stopped abruptly due to the economic problem in the country at that time because celluloid is very expensive to produce. As a result of this, video became an alternative outlet for theatre practitioners to express their talents.

The Imperatives of Costume and Make-up Design in Nigeria video film:

Most Nigeria video films depict the real Nigerian indigenous experience. According to Ladebo, video films have been a good source of recapturing Nigerian historical past in a most uncompromising style, language possible and costume design” (154).

Costume:

Costume is the common indigenous feature found in the Nigeria video film. Costumes are clothes worn by performers which are intended both to impress an audience and help interpret the character. They are described as the garments and accessories worn or carried by performers, using wigs and related head coverings, masks, face putting and a host of other materials used to transform or modify facial appearance (Encyclopedia Americana, vol. 7). The terms “dress” and “costume” are often used interchangeably in language, because they serve the same basic purpose although in different circumstances. However costume can be said to go beyond the basic functions of dress. Umukoro says that, “a costume is usually a dress, which by some restriction, is set apart as a unit of its own, restrictions such as may be imposed by functionality or origin”(48). The importance of dress in human society cannot be over emphasised man’s identity can be known through his dress code.

In any drama production, costume sends signal similar to everyday life. Costume functions as a language that can indicate a character’s age, gender, marital status, place of origin, religion, social status or occupation. It provides considerable information about the

character, including individual personality, economic standing and position. Costume also differentiates the characters, for instance master to servant. Wilson in his contribution states that, costume “indicates status in life, occupations, and personalities and shows the relationship between the characters separating the major character from the minor character” (361). In the same vein, Ommanney and Achanker opine that costume, “is worn to express the personality of the character; revealing social status, taste and idiosyncrasies. It should aid the audience’s understanding of the actor’s relationship to the other characters and to the play itself”(348). This goes to say that the status of the character that the actor is represented can be identified through the costume. Costume can be used to reflect characters that are in opposition. Thus, costume in any drama production aids the audience to recognize the characters and their personality.

Costume design is the construction of apparel for the overall appearance of the character. This usually involves research, designing, and building the actual items from inception. The costume designer according to Oscar Brockett, “must be well grounded in social and cultural history, (including the visual arts, dance and theatre) because clothing reflects the mores, standards of beauty and stylistic preference of period and place (397). The costume designer must do a thorough research about daily life, occupation, class structure, and the things the society enjoys doing most. In the same vein, Umukoro opines that, “the need for a costume designer to have more than a vague knowledge of the history, culture and people of the ethnic background against which a particular drama is set, cannot be over emphasized”(50).

Costume for any drama production should aid the interpretation of the story. It should be based on the director’s vision and in accordance with all the designs of the other designers, like lighting designer, scenic designer and in the fore front, production designer. The actor should be costumed to depict his/her character and the message of the film. The costume designer should not seek to beautify the performers or actors but to enhance his/her role with such costume. W.C.Robert is of the opinion that, “costume reveal and define both the play’s character and the meaning of its action. It also has a direct and interesting relationship to the language the actor speaks.”(273). Most importantly, costume designers and make-up artists must read the script thoroughly before initiating ideas. The analysis of the script expands beyond the printed letters to include the views and the interpretations of the director, production, and other designers. Thus, there is need for the costume designer to be familiar with the interpretation of colors and fabric. Gillette, states that, “part of his or her historical research will acquaint the costume designer with the color and types of fabrics used in a particular historical period. This information needs to be manipulated in design process”(385).

Make-up:

In any drama production, (screen, television or stage) make-up is any material used by actors for cosmetic purposes and as an aid in taking on the appearance appropriate to the characters they play. Make-up is said to be the complement to costume in any production. Make-up which is essentially the design of the actor’s face seems sorely neglected in modern productions. It tends to be the last design to be considered. Usually make-up is applied for the first time at the final rehearsal before shooting and sometimes not until just

before the camera man or director of photography calls the shots. Make-up is given a deeper meaning in the various ways in which the body could be decorated for different purposes and for different occasions. Make-up is given a deeper meaning in the various traditional African societies; different parts of the body are painted, identification marks are made on the faces, chest, back, legs and arms. According to Gillette, “make-up is a vital element in creating the total appearance of the actor... gives the audience its primary clue to the age, health and vitality of the character”(432). In the same vein, Brockett posits that, “make-ups establish the age of a character, state of health, race, profession, basic attitude, in addition to psychological qualities”(363).

The make-up artist must plan according to the lighting of the production. In essence, he or she must work together with other designers so as to know the overall production design. The make-up artist must have a very good knowledge of the facial bones and muscles, and understanding of tone and color for him or her to be able to apply the right shade of color in any film production. Just as Ommanney and Schanker opine, “bone structure is the key to facial make-up”(374). Make-up just like costume is regarded as an enhancer of visual messages.

According to Fielschhacker, make-up “aids the actors in projecting their characters to the audience... it aids final touch of an actor’s stage personality”(213). Similarly, Ommanney and Schanker go further to observe that make-up, “help present the external appearance of the internally created role”(374). On its own part, Wilson opines that makeup, “serves as an additional tone for the performance in creating an image of the character”(367). Hence, the appropriate application of make-up helps the actor to portray his character effectively and it gives the actor the fill of the character he is assuming.

Make-up is used to overcome the bleaching effect of strong light, because when the light is focused on the skin it tends to lighten up. By thoughtful design, colors can be made more appropriate to the character than the actor’s natural skin tone. Gillette said that, “on a more mundane level, bright stage light tends to lighten skin tones, so make-up is used to put the color back in the cheek of the actor” (432) . Similarly, Herbert disclosed that “light on warm colors (warm reds, oranges, brown, tans) shows a lighter skin that appears slightly washed out and lights on cool colors (blue reds, blues, blue green) appears darker”(370). Thus, correctly make-up color against correctly lighting system must be chosen to compensate for these distortions.

Make-up for any production can be classified into straight: (which utilizes the actor’s own basic characteristics without altering them significantly), corrective make-up: (which seeks to reduce less pleasing facial characteristics, while enhancing more attractive points. The actual treatment in corrective make-up can range from slight modification of lips, eyes, nose, to strapping, sagging skin or outstanding ears or concealing baldness) and character make-up: (which totally changes the actors own appearance). In character make-up, emphasis is upon the specific character the actor is playing.

The Need for Appropriate Costume and Makeup in Nigeria Video Film:

Costume, make-up, sets, location, technical effects and lighting designs are very important in the interpretation of the director’s message in any film production. These elements can also strongly influence the way a film production is perceived by the audience,

either by creating a mood (somber or festive, depending on the color or ornamentation used) or by strengthening a director's vision or concept. The possibility of creating appropriate costume design helps in creating a good aesthetic visual appeal. This appeal is achieved when costume is in complement with other elements of visual composition aforementioned. As a result, the use of appropriate costumes for a film production enhances the aesthetic value of the film. Hence an inconsistent costume design of a film production creates a visual fatigue and boredom. There is the need for consistency in the use of costume, with every element of the theatre, so as to give the appropriate effect of harmony. This calls for a special consultation or cooperation with the designers involved. Wilson, opines that, "Costumes must be consistent with the entire production, especially with the various other elements" (326).

The costume and make-up of any production can achieve appropriate consistency and coherence, when the designers, in charge, help in the planning of the overall design, putting characteristics such as texture, colors and shapes into consideration. Thus the ultimate goal of a costume and make-up designer is to aim at conceiving appropriate design for a particular story or film, For instance, costume and make-up materials for epic video films should have the impression of the period. Though, the costume and make-up designers as creative artists are not tied to the exact materials used at the period. Thus, they can decide to create a design, using the historical materials as a reference point. According to Gillette, "theatrical costumes may be faithful to their historical period, or the costume designer may choose to use history as a reference point from which to create a design that is more meaningful to the production concept for a particular play"(389). In this vein, the designer must always be meaningfully creative. Historical clothing must be accurate and believable for today's eyes.

Truth, at times, may be sacrificed to ensure that an actor looks correct and the designer must determine how to make departures from strict historical accuracy appropriate to both the period and to the actor's physique. The designer must know the history well enough to twist it, if necessary, without losing an accurate feel for the time. Hence, costume designers and make-up artists should endeavor to create good artistic image of the period, locale, as well as the costume and make-up. This can only be achieved through research into these cultures, which have been a futile effort on the part of most designers. This is why Ekwuazi confirms that:

the Nigerian home video has continued to produce those negative and stereotype images which find a resonance in Western consciousness... the west repackages and propagates those same images...western correspondent reporting Africa filters his dispatches through the layers of those same stereotype and negative images...(7).

This implies that Nigeria video film productions were greatly influenced by western images which do not really concentrate much on Nigeria indigenous designs, most especially set and costume design, and are not properly handled. For costume and make-up design to be appropriate, it is pertinent for Nigeria film makers to fall back to Nigeria indigenous culture in order to recreate good visual images of the Nigeria culture. In the light of this, Okome opines that, "the need to discourage influences from American, Asian film cultures have become very pressing lately because popular indigenous films are thought to represent a

distinct cultural world with recognizable social institutions ...” (107). Nigeria video film should portray cultural aesthetics and project Nigerian rich cultural heritage, instead of portraying themes that are either violent ritualistic, murderous or western in nature.

In film production, emphasis on certain features of production design should be noted especially in the areas of costume and make-up. It is through these production design features that effective communication can be enhanced in film. According to Gillette, “a great deal of communication process that transfers information from the actor to the audience takes place visually” (432). In essence, costume and make-up enhances actor’s role interpretation to the better understanding and long lasting impression on the audience. The actor is the central figure upon whom all the process of action must be placed in order to get at the target of drama production. The producers, directors and all designers use the actors in expressing and communicating their thoughts to the audience. Of all these, costume and make-up seem to be closer to the actor. Wilson opines that, “the most personal are costume along with make-up, hair style and masks because they are worn by the performers themselves. Visually, the performer and the costume are perceived as one...”(358).

In creating a character’s image for a production, appropriate costume and make-up should be applied. For instance, when a character is meant to be aged, it is expected of the make-up artist to give the actor a character make-up that will de-emphasize the actor’s personality. Consequently, the conformity of costume and make-up design with other elements of the production design strikes a balance in the visual composition of a film. For costume to be appropriate, it should meet the following seven requirements, enumerated by Edwin Wilson; (i) help establish the tone and style of a production, (ii) indicate the nature of individual characters or groups in a play, their stations in life, (iii) their occupations, their personalities, (iv) indicate the historical period of a play and the locale in which it occurs, (v) show the relationship among the characters, separating major characters from minor ones, contracting one group with another, (vi) where appropriate symbolically convey the significance of individual characters or the theme of the play, (vii) meet the needs of individual performers, be consistent (356).

Communicative roles of costume and make-up in video film:

According to Storm, communication is, “the transmission by symbols of information and ideas. It is the most modern theory of the function of dress ... communication is a function of all dress that has evolved in organized societies with roles and statuses” (102). Costume is a non-verbal mode of communication. Costume communicates as much as verbal language. Costume and all its accessories are of great importance in film production. Apart from using costumes to interpret or impersonate a character, they add color, shape, texture and symbolic quality to the overall visual effect of any film production. Costumes in film or stage productions are not just materials, they are signs and statements of who we are. “Costume is a visual statement of the individual, about just who we are and to which group we have allegiance” (Storm, 104). Costume as non-verbal communication represents other information, apart from them. On a symbolic level, costumes acquire semiotic meanings, thereby changing into a sign.

Costumes along with scenery and lighting, inform the viewer about the style of a play, whether it is a tragedy, a comedy or a tragic-comedy. Costumes should be able to

depict the appropriate mood and tone of that production. For instance, if a drama is tragedy, the costume will be somber and dignified; seeing them, the audience would know immediately that the drama itself is somber, and the tone will be serious. Costume indicates the period and locale of a play. Whether it is historical, epic or contemporary, it indicates whether it is set in Africa, or Europe. Costumes tell us when and where the action occurred. Sometimes the costume designer and the director decide to shift the period of a play. According to Gillette:

... any historical period regardless whether it is one or forty years long, has a plethora of design styles, and each of those styles has an overwhelming number of subtle variations. If the costume designer were to randomly select costume elements from the entirety of the period, the result would be a visual hodge podge(385).

Synopsis of Worlds Apart:

The film, **Worlds Apart with parts I and II** is a contemporary drama, partly set in an imaginary town, 'Awada Land' is in Edo State of Nigeria and partly in a remote village on the eastern Igbo area. The movie features Laz Ekwueme as King Idoto, Liz Benson as Mirabel, Kenneth Okonkwo as Promise(The Prince), Hilda Dokubo as Rhoda, Bruno Iwuoha as Benedict, Gentle Jack as Jekwu, Ini Edo as Ulimma, Geraldine Ekeocha as Thelma, Charles Awurum as Godwin, etc. The Costumier was Uche Nancy, Make-up artist was Jessica Nnamani. The video film was produced by Sunny Collins and Directed by Tchidi Chikere. Ulimma was from a poor family in a village untouched by modernity. She was taken to the township to become a house girl for her uncle and his wife. It was her first time in the city. Uli, played by Ini Edo, was warned by an elder in her village before she left for the city, never to get, *"talons like a witch, also that the city girls dip their mouth in blood before they go out, ... and they call it lipstick"*.

In the movie, we saw Uli's childlike amazement at all things technological. When a car goes past the house she hides behind the gateman because the sounds and speed are unfamiliar to her. She was scared but at the same time in awe. From becoming scared, she became obsessed with the cars. Uli loves to watch the King's procession of cars go by and positions herself every day to watch, as she gleefully tells the gateman, *"Look how it shines like the sun! Me I like nice things o!"* Also we see the Prince, played by Kenneth Okonkwo as he begins to take notice of Uli, as she stands out every day, watching the procession of cars go past. In a show of humility, the Prince despite his royal background, was a very humble man. On one occasion, his driver laid out red carpet for him to walk on, from the house to the car, but he refused to walk on it, walking instead on the pavement beside the carpet.

After several efforts made, the Prince finally got to know Uli and became very fond of her; which led to a marriage proposal. The queen was outraged that her son has brought in a girl with no social standing, wealth or affluence and thus demeans her at every possible chance. The Prince with the king supporting him financially, secured a well furnished apartment for Ulimma and her mother. The apartment thus served as a hide-out for the pair while the Prince, determined to transform them into city breeds, employed special teachers for them. After the grooming period, the Prince introduced Ulimma to his mother as his

fiancée using a fake identity. Having introduced her as the daughter of a late minister with the assumed name 'Lillian', Queen Mirabel Idoto, without question, approved and began the wedding arrangements immediately. After the marriage ceremony, Prince Promise and his wife revealed the truth to the Queen. When the deception was revealed to the queen, she realizes her earlier mistake and begged for forgiveness.

Costume and Make-up in the video film:

The choice of costume and make-up design in 'Worlds Apart' indicates the locale of the play and the events as it unfolds. From the beginning of the film, the beautiful Edo cultural heritage was established, through the use of costume and make-up. This displays the aesthetic value and creates an atmosphere of beauty, with the carefully selected colors that were used. The use of colors was basically for emphasis, tone and mood. The costume designer used costume to show how rich and sophisticated the Edo culture is. Costume was also used to reflect how poor Ulimma's family was. The costume designer, with her design, distinguished between royal personage and others. For instance, in the film 'Worlds Apart', king Idoto, Queen Mirabel and the Prince, were dressed in flamboyant costumes, in colors usually associated with royalty. Queen Mirabel Idoto, throughout the film was always in Edo royal paraphernalia. Her costume fabrics, color design and accessories all indicate royalty. The costume designer (Uche Nancy) costumed the King and Queen in modern Edo royal costume.

Analysis of some character's costume and make-up in the video film:

King Idoto:-The King of Awada land was always in his royal regalia, which was made of Eyon (Beads top) and worn on top of wrapper (igbeigbe), tied a few inches away from the chest down to the feet. He was costumed in a beaded crown and all other accessories, like bead worn on his hands. The costume designer used two patterns in costuming the king. He was costumed for staying in the palace and his costume pattern, for outing differs in such way that he is costumed with long sleeved top and wrapper, his beaded crown and staff of office. His make-up also depicts his royal status.

Queen Mirabel Idoto:-The queen being a sophisticated, intimating and discriminating woman was well costumed for her role. The costume used by Queen Mirabel was basically assorted types of wrapper, including George, velvet and very many others. The wrapper was usually tied on the chest region and knotted at the back. The wine and purple colored fabric (velvet) used are specially designed for Oba's wife in Edo. Usually, the staff of office carefully was stitched to the wrapper; this places the queen in her own unique class. The special hair style known as Okuku, is decorated with beads and is worn only by the royal personage. The use of beads around the wrist and neck region adds regalia to her class. Her facial make-up was always straight and glamorous, as she wears a well polished finger nails, befitting a queen of her status.

Ulimma: -Uli the peasant house girl, before becoming a royal personage, was costumed by the costume designer, in different big blouses and skirts and unkempt hair do. When her fortune changed, her costume revealed her new status as the wife of the heir apparent to the throne of Awada land. She was costumed virtually the same way as Queen Mirabel and wore flashy and polished make-ups befitting her new status.

Prince Promise: -He was a very simple man without discrimination. He was man with a modest taste. This was revealed in the way he was costumed. All his costumes were stylish and in bright royal colors, adorned with calm and gentle make-ups.

Conclusion

This research set out to study the role of costume and make-up in Nigeria video films. As a means of visual communication, the costume an actor wears tells the kind of role he is playing. Costume and make-up create the mood, tone and style in a film production. In the study, an attempt was made to examine critically, the imperatives of the use of costume and make-up in Nigeria video film. An attempt was also be made in discussing the need for appropriate costume and make-up designs in the chosen Nigeria video film. The research revealed the communicative functions of costume in the named Nigeria video film. Costume and make-up in any drama production (whether screen or stage) reveal and enhance communication through fabric, color, and line. It also reveals the actor's race, environment, social class and economic status, locale and style, mood, and many other paraphernalia targeted at enriching needed communication affects and effects.

Costume and make-up can be used to indicate change in a character's status, occupation and position, just as well revealed in 'Worlds Apart', Ulimma and her family were elevated from poverty to riches, and this also changes every other thing concerning them, most especially their costume and make-up. The choice of materials and colors in costuming and how it appeals to the audience, are being treated in the study as a visual element of effective communication. How a character is costumed, often tells the audience, at first glance, the kind of role that particular actor is playing. Costuming is not just taking some clothing off the street and putting them on the actors. Costume and make-up must be created to suit a particular performer, the role and circumstances as well as a consideration of its aesthetic appeal to the entire production. It has been noted that costume and make-up materials enhance effective communication in Nigerian video films. This study, as an additional contribution to knowledge, is expected to generate further inquiry in scholarship. Hopefully, it shall draw greater attention to the potential of costume and make-up in the communication chain, by addressing such problems that may lead to its otherwise wrong usage in character and scene portrayal.

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